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Concept of Conservation of Natural Resources in Ancient Indian literature

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Abstract

Our ancient literature including the Vedas is universally accepted as most precious Indian heritage. Veda has the concept of nature and life. Environment protection and purifying the environment is the essence of Vedic literature. Environment consists of biotic and abiotic components. Biotic component includes both plant (flora) and animal (fauna). Trees are considered most important and there are many practices adopted to protect the trees. They are considered as God and ritual element. Some plants are worshipped daily, some on the basis of tithi and some for special cause, in this way conservation of trees is suggested in our ancient literature. A verse of Rigveda says "Thousand and hundreds of years if you want to enjoy the fruits and happiness of life then take up systematic planting of trees". According to a verse of Matsya Purana, "one plant is equivalent to ten sons and is more worth than ten sons". Many animals are considered auspicious, that's why harm to them is punishable in the ancient literature. There are certain conservation practices suggested for threatened animals. Universe is made from panchmahabhutas i.e., water, earth, air, sky and fire which are abiotic components of environment. Water is an essential element for life. Earth is considered as mother, sky as father, air as prana vayu and fire as the source of energy. There is a verse "yatha bramhande tatha pinde", that means, if there is any disturbance in any of these elements of universe, it will also harm the elements of our body, resulting in the health issues. Our ancient literature is full of environment friendly practices. The aim of this article is to make aware the today's youth with these ancient environmental conservation practices and adopt as a part of their daily life.

Keywords

Environment, Conservation, Plants, Animals, Veda.

Introduction

Our ancient Indian literature includes Vedas, Puranas, Upanishads, Ramayana and Shrimad Bhagwat Geeta etc. Vedas are universally accepted most precious Indian heritage. Veda has the concept of nature and life. Environment protection and purifying the environment is the essence of Vedic literature. Our ancient Indian literature is having the concept of environment friendly activities. Hindu philosophy has the concept of conservation of biodiversity (both flora and fauna) and environment (water, earth, air and space) (<https://vsktelangana.org>).

Vedas have the concept of worship of three kind of gods, which includes -nature/terrestrial god (Prithvi, Agni, Vayu, Brahaspati and Soma), atmospheric gods (Indra, Rudra, Marut, Vayu and Parjanya) and celestial gods (Dyaus, Varuna, Ushas and Asvins) (Sarma, 2015).

There are four Vedas, namely Rig Veda, Atharva Veda, Yajur Veda and Sama Veda. These Vedas are full of knowledge about God, Soul and physical universe (Talwar, 2005). Rigveda is oldest Sanskrit text. Rigveda is consisting of Samhita, Brahmanas, Aranyakas and Upanishads. Vedas along with Ramayana, Mahabharata and Bhagwat Geeta are giving the messages of environment protection and sustainable use of natural resources.

Objective of study

The aim of this article is to make aware the today's youth with these ancient environmental conservation practices and adopt as a part of their daily life

Review of Literature

The conservation of natural resources has been in practice since the Vedic period. Tridev lord Bramha, Vishnu and Mahesha are considered to maintain life on earth, as they perform the role of creation, nourishment and destruction. Environment is made up of five elements (Shivkumar and Rao, 2004). Conservation of flora and fauna is a must to maintain life on earth. Importance of tree quoted in Shrimad Bhagwat Geeta (Pandey, 2019). In Rigveda, Yajurveda, Matsya purana and Sakanda purana many verses are dedicated to the importance of plants. Conservation of plants was mentioned in Vedas and various ancient literature with ritual of their worship (Chaturvedi, ignica.nic.in). All five elements are associated with God as mentioned in Vedas. Water element is known as apas in vedic literature. Yajurveda and Prithvi Sukta of Atharvaveda are dedicated to sustainable utilization of earth elements. Yagya is considered as Vedic technique to make the atmosphere healthy (Sharma et al., 2014; Davender, 2019; Khatmura, 2019; Agrawal et al., 2024).

Methodology

The present paper is based on secondary data collected from various books, journals, websites and articles etc.

Analysis**History of Concept**

Our Vedas are very much concerned about the protection of our natural resources. Vedas will guide to enlighten the inner human soul in order to maintain moral values, true purpose of life and care of nature. Vedas use several terms to undertone nature or environment viz. Jagat, Vishva, Prakriti and Prapancha. Jagat represents the perishable nature of the world. Vishva is represented by nature's capacity to enter each particle of the universe. Prakriti indicates that environment is created with a purpose. Prapancha means the environment is created by five elements or panch bhutas i. e. earth, water, fire wind and space (Sivakumar and Rao, 2004). All these elements are interconnected and they form a cycle Figure 1.

Fig.1- Five Elements

In Vedas everything either living or non-living is considered as a life (Sarma,2015). There are two components in the atmosphere, i. e. biotic and abiotic. Biotic component includes plants and animals. Pandey in 2019, quoted shlokas of Shrimad Bhagwat Geeta in which importance of trees was mentioned.

पश्यैतान् महाभागान् परार्थेकान्तजीवितान् ।
 वातवर्षातपहिमान् सहन्तरे वारयन्ति नः ॥
 अहो एषां वरं जन्म सर्वं प्राण्युपजीवनम् ।
 सुजनस्यैव येषां वै विमुखा यान्ति नार्थिनः ॥
 पुत्रपुष्पफलच्छाया मूलवल्कलदारुभिः ।
 गन्धनिर्यासभस्मास्थितोस्मैः कामात् वितन्वते ॥
 एतावज्जन्मसाफल्यं देहिनामिह देहिषु ।
 प्राणैरर्थधिया वाचा श्रेय एवाचरेत् सहा ॥ श्रीमद् भागवत 10.22.32-35 ॥

Shrimad Bhagwat Geeta says that trees are great, they spend their life for benevolence. They tolerate the extremes of the climate like storms, rains and cold. Their life is great, because they help other living beings to survive. They are just like a gentleman from whose door no solicitor will go back empty. They provide us leaves, flower, fruit, shelter, roots, bark, timber and fuel. Besides this they provide us fragrance, ash, seeds and seedlings and fulfill our wishes.

A quote from Vishnu Purana says “One who plants a peepal, one neem, one banyan, ten flowering plants or creepers, two pomegranate, two orange and five mango trees will not go to hell.”

There are two types of plants, cryptogams (seedless plants) and phanerogams (seed bearing plants). Many seed plants are used in various rituals. Plants used in rituals from birth to death can be classified into two categories, i. e. in form of God element and ritual material. Trees which are used as a god in various rituals are known as God element trees. These can be further categorized into 3 forms- God form, God symbol form and God residing form. God form plants are of 3 types viz. daily worshipped, worshipped on tithi and worshipped just for cause. Daily worshipped plants are holy basil (Haripriya-tulsi) and Peepal. Table I includes those plants which are worshipped on tithi.

Plants	Tithi of worship
Indian Goose Berry/ Amla	Amla Navmi
Durva	Doobri Saten
Aak	Akua chhat
Banana	Thursday
Peepal	Saturday

Table I- Plants worshipped on tithi

Plants worshipped for special cause are mentioned in the table II

For well being	
Aak	To get the child
Shami	To get victory
Banyan tree	For long life of husband
Protection from negative energy	
Peepal	Tantrik
Aak	Tantrik

Table II: Plants worshipped for special cause

Plants like Ashok, Castor, Neem, Kadam, Bael, Lotus, Rudraksh and Gular are also considered as God form plants. God symbol plants are turmeric and beetle nut. God resides form, are those whose parts are supposed to have residence of God/deity. They also classified into three types, they are God form, evil form, ancestor form. Banana, Shami and Aak is worshipped as God form. Cluster fig, Bamboo, Ziziphus and Peepal are represented as evil form (Chaturvedi, ignica.nic.in).

Our many rituals are centred on worship of plants/ trees. Most of the Hindu families worship the Tulsi plant daily and in Kartik month of Hindu calendar. It is a belief that worship of Lord Vishnu and Krishna is incomplete without the Tulsi patra, so we are plucking the leaves for worship. Tulsi plant is treasure of medicinal properties, so it is used in many home remedies and commercially exploited for medicine preparations. Foresight of saints gave some instructions to prevent over exploitation of this holy and medicinal plant. Their instructions are not to pluck the leaves on Sunday, Wednesday and Ekadadashi tithi.

Banyan tree also has religious and medicinal importance. Hindu ladies perform Vat Savitri pooja under the tree and also worship the tree. Due to religious belief human beings cannot destroy or cut it. Amla tree is worshipped on Amla Navami. There is a ritual, ladies spend few time beneath the tree on that particular tithi. As we all know fruits of this plant are rich source of vitamin-C and immunity booster. Morally no one cut the worshipped trees. Banana plant is worshipped on Thursday by unmarried young girls to get an ideal bridegroom. Banana plant is used during the poojas and wedding ceremonies. Banana leaves are used as plate for eating food. Similarly, Mango, Shami/ Khejadi, Durva, Kusha, Pomegranate and many other plants are used for worship, to prevent their over exploitation certain rules are prepared.

A verse of Rig Veda says “Thousand and Hundreds of years if you want to enjoy the fruits and happiness of life, then take up systematic planting of trees” (Sharma, <https://www.biotechjournal.in>).

In all most all ancient literature, Peepal tree (Ashwattha vriksha) is considered auspicious and its every part is considered as residence of deity. Peepal tree is mostly worshipped on Saturday. It is clear in the following verse of Skand purana.

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मूले विष्णुः स्थितो नित्यं स्कन्धे केशव एव च

नारायाणस्तु शाखासु पत्रेषु भगवान् हरिः ।

फलेऽच्युते न सन्देहः सर्वदेवै समन्वितः।

स एव विष्णुर्द्रुम एव मूर्ती

महात्मभिः सेवितपुण्यमूलम।

यस्याश्रयः पापसहस्रहन्ता

भवेन्नृणां कामदुघो गुणाढ्यः ॥ स्कन्द पुराण 247.41॥

Above verse of Skand Prana says that Vishnu resides in the root of peepal tree, Keshav resides in the stem, Narayan in branches, Lord Hari in the leaves. In this way the religious significance of tree is mentioned. So, destroyer of this tree is supposed to be punished like bramhahatya.

In the Vedas and puranas cutting of tree is prohibited and punishable also. All these shlokas we can say their foresight for sustainable use of resources is very appropriate in the present scenario.

Yajurveda salute to trees and forests, which is mentioned in the following quote-

नमो वृक्षेभ्यः । Yajurveda 16.17

वनानां पतये नमः । Yajurveda 16.18

औषधीनां पतये नमः । Yajurveda 16.19

वृक्षाणां पतये नमः । Yajurveda 16.18

रण्यानां पतये नमः । Yajurveda 16.20

Trees or forests are the sources of oxygen, so they are considered as the source of prana vayu. Plants can absorb the carbon dioxide (one of the causes of global warming) and other poison from the air, so their conservation was suggested in our heritage literature. Roots of plants are capable of holding the soil; therefore, they are essential to maintain proper earth cover.

According to a verse of Matsya Purana, one plant is equivalent to ten sons and more important than the sons.

दशकूपासमा वापी दशवापीसमो हृदः ।

दशहृदसमः पुत्रो दशपुत्रसमो द्रुमः ॥ मत्स्य पुराण 154 -592॥

Above written verse says one baoli is equivalent to ten wells. One pond is equivalent to ten baolis. Ten ponds equal to a son and ten sons equivalent to a tree. So, in this way trees are most important for the survival of living beings.

म काकम्बीरमुद्वृहो वनस्पतिमशस्तीर्वि हि नीनशः।

मोत सूरो अह एवा चन ग्रीवा आदधते वेः॥ Rig Veda 6.48.17॥

This verse of Rigveda says sacred trees like banyan which are nurturing the crows should not be destroyed. Their sins must be removed and used with certain remedies. Do not harm any living being like cruelty of eagle, who kill the birds by gripping their neck. This clearly indicates that human being should be protective for the plants and must be kind for other living beings. It is a message for the conservation of biodiversity.

Vedas alarmed us about deforestation, excessive cutting and over exploitation of forest resources which results in the climate change. Problem of climate change is a big threat to coming generations.

Another important biotic factor in environment are the consumers and their conservation is equally important to balance the nature. Cow is considered as kamdhenu of our planet. Due to importance of Panch gavya in our life, cow is considered as Gomata.

It was suggested that if you feed crow, it will reach to your ancestors. Crow is a scavenger and rare species. Therefore, it is in practice to feed crows in bhadrpad krishna paksha with a belief it will reach to our ancestors. This practice is applied to save crows and indirectly to save the peepal and banyan tree. Snake is a poisonous creature, which play a crucial role in maintenance of food chain in ecosystem. Due to their poisonous nature everyone is afraid and try to kill them for own safety. To save this threatened animal, our ancient culture gave a ritual of nag pooja on Nag Panchami in Shravan month.

Abiotic factor includes water, earth, air, space and fire. In Mahabharata nature is cosmic being, mountains are considered as bones, earth as flesh, sea as blood, sky as abdomen, air as breath and fire as energy. In Vedic concept you cannot separate yourself from nature.

Water is very essential for life. As we all know 70-80% water is present in human body. There is no life without water. In Rig Veda, there are several Gods attributed to water. In four suktas of rig Veda Apas, is considered as God of water. Others gods for water are Indra, Varun, Prajanya etc. (Saxena, 2012).

Yajurveda says "Do not poison water and do not harm or cut the trees," here poison word is used for pollution, at that time the word pollution was not introduced.

Natural water resources are contaminated with waste water and become harmful for the living beings. Depletion in dissolved oxygen results in the death of aquatic as well as terrestrial organisms. Charka says-

पिच्छिलं कृमिलं क्लिन्नं पर्णशैवालकर्दमैः ।

विवर्णं विरसं सान्द्रं दुर्गन्धं न हितं जलम् ॥

Water having mucilage, worms, decomposing algae and leaves, discolored, bad taste and with foul smell is useless. This water can cause many diseases. A shloka of Padma Purana restricts the mankind for excretion of urine and faeces on the banks of water bodies.

In Rigveda goddess earth is known as Prithvi. It is one of the five elements/ panch mahabhootas of universe. It is considered as mother. Atharvaveda considered us as a son of earth -

माता भूमिः पुत्रोऽहं पृथिव्याः (92.1.12), it is quoted in the Sloka no. 12 of Pruthvi sukta of Atharva Veda) It indicates that our Vedic culture was very much concerned about the environment protection

द्याम्मा लेखीरन्तरिक्षम्मा हिँसीः पृथिव्या संभव ।

अयँ हि त्वा स्वधितिस्तेतिजानः प्रणिनाय महते सौभगाय ।

अतस्त्वन्देव वनस्पते शतवल्शो विरोह सहस्रवल्शा वि वयँ रुहेम ॥ Yajurveda 5.43 ॥

There is a prayer for over exploitation of earth in Hymm no 12, shlok no. 34 of Atharva Veda, Prithvi Sukta. "Whatever I dig from thee, O Earth, may that have quick recovery again. O purifier, may we be not injuring thy vitals or thy heart" (Sarma N, 2005).

Pran vayu is essential for life. Pran vayu means oxygen is present in sufficient amount in the air. Our ancient literature, Vedas and Upanishads mentioned air purification technique called as Yagya. Yajurveda is one of the four Vedas, having primarily of prose mantras for worship rituals. These mantras are recited during the Yajana before the yajna fire. Yagya is the process in which specific herbs are sacrificed in the fire with rhythmic

mantra chanting (Davender, 2019). Similar concept is mentioned in Sam Veda (63) and Rig Veda.

अग्निवृत्राणि दयते पुरूणि ॥ Rig Veda 10.80.2 ॥

आ जुहोता हविषा मजयध्वम् (साम. 63) ।

Sharma and his co-workers (2014) mentioned that Agnihotra is basically a healing process. Khatmura (2019) mentioned that according to Geeta Yajna results in purification of nature, plenty of rains and origin of food etc. nature balancing activities. Agrawal and her coworkers (2024) mentioned that Yajna is therapy for both mankind and environment.

Conclusion In conclusion this review paper suggested that, our ancient literature is full of eco-friendly practices and treasure of nature conservation practices. There is a science behind every practice advised in ancient Indian literature. It is need of time to find the science behind them and adopt it in practice. It becomes our responsibility to aware the youth about various valuable practices discussed in ancient Indian literature. This paper reviewed and discussed few of the eco-friendly practices mentioned in our ancient Indian literature.

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